

Monitoring The Structural Condition of Composite Industrial Parts Through Embedded Optical Sensorization

ICCM24 – 24th International Conference on Composite Materials
August 4 – 8, 2025, Baltimore – USA

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INTRODUCTION

Damage in Composite Materials

Damage mode types on impacted composite laminate

Embedded Sensorization: A Smart Solution for Composite Health Monitoring

Optical Fiber Sensors:

Fibre Bragg Grating (FBG) sensors

Advantages

- + compatibility with composites fabrication
- + reduced cabling as several FBG sensors can be multiplexed in the same OF
- + high sensitivity
- + ability to monitor the fabrication process and curing
- + capability of impact damage detection
- + localized strain measurement
- + immunity to electromagnetic interference
- + Durability

Disadvantages

- expensive optoelectronic interrogation system
- fragility
- localized strain measurement

Fibre Bragg Grating (FBG) sensors

$$\Delta \epsilon = \Delta \lambda_S \times S_\epsilon$$

$$\Delta T = \Delta \lambda_T \times S_T$$

Strain – Temperature compensation

CASE STUDY 1

Monitoring of Composite Overwrapped Pressure Vessels

Objectives

- Establish a baseline of FBG sensors data for the current manufacturing process (Winding, Curing and *Autofrettage*) and pressure cycling fatigue test
- Measurement of strain in all manufacturing and testing stages
- Assess the contribution of different layers (at location of FBG sensors) to the overall mechanical resistance of the SCBA tanks

SCBA tank specimens

Specimen	OF Supplier	Manufacturing variations
1	A	External heating during heating of CF/epoxy prepreg tape winding
2	B	No use of external heating

Winding of CF composite layers of SCBA tank 1 with applied external heating

FBG sensors Integration Methodology

Summary of embedded OFs

OF	No. FBG sensors	Sensor type	Location
OF _{LINER}	5		Liner Surface
OF _{INT}	3	mechanical and thermal strain	In between internal CF circumferential layers and helical layers
OF _{EXT}	3		In between last circumferential CF and GF layers
OF _{TEMP}	1	temperature variations	In between same layers as OF _{EXT} . FBG _{TEMP} positioned next to FBG1 on OF _{EXT}

FBG sensors Integration

OF_{LINER}

OF_{INT}

OF_{EXT} & OF_{TEMP}

Manufacturing – Winding

Loading of the instrumented liner on the winding equipment

Winding of first intermediate helical layer

Loading of SCBA tank specimen in the GF winding equipment

Winding Monitoring

Measured strain, by FBG_{L-C2} close to the liner, during winding of different layers

Winding Stages		Tank 1 (FBG L-C2)	Tank 2 (FBG L-C2)
0	Before Winding	0	0
1	1Circf	795	-77
2	2Circf	1333	-103
3	3Circf	1282	-128
4	4Circf	1205	-154
5	Hel15	1385	-77
6	Hel66	1256	-179
7	1Circf int	1231	-256
8	2Circf int	564	-179
9	Hel int	-	-128
10	1Circf ext	-	-179
11	Hel GF	-	-26
12	1Circf GF	-	-103
13	2Circf GF	-	-77
14	3Circf GF	-	-128

Manufacturing – Curing

(a) instrumented SCBA tank specimen in the oven for curing and (b) data acquisition set up outside of it

Typical curing schedule

Curing Monitoring

SCBA tank 1

Central wavelength changes measured by FBG sensors in the SCBA tank 1

SCBA tank 2

Central wavelength changes measured by FBG sensors in the SCBA tank 2

Curing Monitoring

SCBA tank 1

SCBA tank 2

Strain and temperature changes for FBG sensors in the OF_{EXT} and OF_{TEMP} placed in between last CF layer and first GF layer in the SCBA tank 1 (left) and tank 2 (right)

Manufacturing – Autofrettage

Stress/strain behaviour of liner, composite overwrap and overall COPV when subject to pressurization during autofrettage and following pressure cycles

Theoretical pressure schedule of the autofrettage process and subsequent hydraulic proof pressure test

Fatigue Pressure Cyclic Test

Instrumented SCBA tank specimen in the fatigue test equipment ready for testing

Pressure cycle employed in the fatigue test

Autofrettage and Fatigue Testing Monitoring

Autofrettage Process

Example of strain measured by FBG sensors in OF_{INT} in SCBA tank 1

Fatigue Testing

Specimen	Number of endured cycles in fatigue test
1	16 281
2	8 234

Comparison of strain measured in FBG_{L-CD} and FBG_{L-C1} sensors, bonded to the liner, on the different SCBA tank specimens

Conclusions

Winding Process: Heating of the wound setup promoted expansion of the liner (tank 1);

Curing: it is possible that full curing conversion is not achieved by the end of the isothermal period, as strain is still slightly decreasing;

Autofrettage:

- The residual strain measured by the FBG sensors confirm that plasticity is successfully imposed on the liner;
- It is possible that tank 1 has suffered higher plasticity in the *autofrettage* process (increased volumetry);

Fatigue Testing:

- FBG sensors in the liner show higher amplitude deformation in SCBA tank 2 (non-heated), which may explain the much faster failure of this specimen;
- The lower strain amplitudes measured in FBG sensors in OF_{LINER} of tank 1 could be linked with the increase of liner's volumetry (plastic deformation) and the consequent higher compression loading induced from the composite (elastic behavior) on the liner;
- Heating of the wound setup during winding, may have contributed to improved fatigue strength due to two factors:
 - (1) the initial expansion of the liner makes the composite to be wound at a larger radius, closer to the final one after autofrettage, causing less fibre breakage after curing and autofrettage;
 - (2) the higher temperature increases resin viscosity promoting improved consolidation of the composite.

CASE STUDY 2

Monitoring of a UAV's spar

Objectives

- Monitor the manufacturing process
- Monitor the structural health condition of the spar, through static and flight testing
- Determine the Remaining Useful Life of the Structure

Optical Sensors Integration

Placement of Optical Fiber Sensors during Manufacturing

Vacuum Bag sealed

Demolded piece after curing

Optical Sensors Integration

Cure Monitoring

Static Test Monitoring

Strain change during Static Loading test

Maximum strain measured during test and residual strain after static test

Sensor	Max. strain (µε)	Residual strain (µε)
FBG2-6	1159.4	-10.9
FBG2-7	989.9	-7.7
FBG2-8	958.3	-4.8
FBG2-9	504.7	-12.6
FBG3-14	-1068.4	-4.3
FBG3-13	-952.3	-4.3
FBG3-12	-1757.2	-4.7
FBG3-11	-2072.7	-23.8
FBG3-10	132.1	36.7

Prediction of the Remaining Useful Life

Strain Analysis of Real-World Irregular Loads

- Real-world strain transient data exhibit irregular behavior over time, making it difficult to count the number of cycles and the life span of that part
- Some methods and algorithms must be implemented to analyze this irregular data;
- Two of them are the Four-Point Method and the RainFlow method

Prediction of the Remaining Useful Life

Four-Point counting Method

The Four-Point Method is a simple algorithm to rapidly assess the incurred cycles across the transient data and indirectly acknowledge the part's fatigue life

Prediction of the Remaining Useful Life

RainFlow counting Method

The Rainflow method is a more robust approach to cycle counting and fatigue assessment;

It extracts the hysteresis cycles and is more precise to extract the damage caused by the “accumulation” of fatigue

Conclusions and Future Work

- The localized strain data allowed to verify the correct curing of the part
- The FBG sensors were able to accurately measure strain during static testing
- The application of cycle counting methods will give important in-situ information about the parts' lifespan, even extending their longevity. Furthermore, the information can be used to predict the most efficient way to plan maintenance operations, reducing the operational costs. Algorithms for the prediction of the Remaining Useful Life of the spar will be developed
- The same spar will be subjected to flight test, with sensing data being acquired in real-time

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